

SESQUITERPENE LACTONES FROM *INULA BRITANNICA***Dusmatova D.,**

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ABSTRACT

The plant *Inula britannica*, a member of the Asteraceae family, is traditionally used in medicine and is listed in the Chinese Pharmacopoeia as a herbal remedy for conditions such as cough, excessive phlegm, nausea, vomiting, and related ailments. As part of our ongoing research on the genus *Inula* L. species growing in Uzbekistan, this work is a part of the phytochemical study of the Uzbek taxon *Inula britannica*. From the chloroform fractions of the ethanolic extracts of the plant's flowers and leaves, sesquiterpene lactones flexuoxin A, ivalin, and britanin were isolated, and their structures were established by spectral methods (^1H , ^{13}C NMR). A minor component, flexuoxin A, was isolated using reversed-phase high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC). The spatial structure of ivalin was determined by X-ray crystallography. Sesquiterpene lactone britanin's *in vitro* cytotoxicity was evaluated against HeLa and HEp-2 cancer cell lines. Britanin demonstrated dose-dependent cytotoxic activity against HeLa and HEp-2 cell lines. At 1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$, cell viability inhibition was $19.4 \pm 0.5\%$ and $2.8 \pm 0.8\%$, respectively, increasing to $77.5 \pm 3.3\%$ (HeLa) and $79.8 \pm 4.0\%$ (HEp-2) at 10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$. The reference drug cisplatin showed stronger activity at 1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ ($81.6 \pm 3.9\%$ for HeLa and $52.8 \pm 3.6\%$ for HEp-2) and at 10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ ($95.0 \pm 5.0\%$ and $89.2 \pm 2.2\%$, respectively). Thus, britanin demonstrates high cytotoxic activity against cervical cancer (HeLa) and laryngeal adenocarcinoma (HEp-2) cells. Conclusion: Overall, the phytochemical analysis of the flowers and leaves of *Inula britannica* revealed the presence of eudesmanolide ivalin, pseudoguaianolides flexuoxin A, and britanin, which exhibited *in vitro* cytotoxic activity against cervical cancer (HeLa) and laryngeal adenocarcinoma (HEp-2) cells.

Keywords: *Inula britannica*; Asteraceae, sesquiterpene lactones, flexuosin A, ivalin, britanin.

INTRODUCTION

Inula britannica L. is a perennial medicinal plant that has been traditionally used in folk and practical medicine for the treatment of various diseases [1]. Recent studies have revealed the antinociceptive activity of the essential oil of *I. britannica* flowers [2], anticonvulsant and sedative-hypnotic activity of compounds from the methanol and aqueous extracts of the aerial parts, with less adverse effects on memory and motor

coordination [3], and neuroprotective activity of *Inula britannica* [4].

This species of the *Inula* L. genus has a very broad natural distribution, as it grows in nearly all regions of Europe and Asia [5].

The population of this plant growing in Europe has been well studied chemically. It has been established that the characteristic metabolites include terpenoids (monoterpenoids, sesquiterpenoids, diterpenoids,

triterpenoids), and phenolic compounds (flavonoids) [1; 5].

It is known that the qualitative and quantitative composition of metabolites in plants can vary depending on the ecological-geographical conditions of their growth and vegetation periods. Therefore, due to its wide application in traditional Uzbek medicine, research has been initiated on the chemical study of the population of *Inula britannica* growing in Uzbekistan [6].

This report presents further research on the phytochemical composition of *Inula britannica* growing in Uzbekistan.

EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

General methods

The melting point was determined using a Melting Point Tester (BMP-M70 model, Biobase, China). The IR spectrum was recorded on a Fourier transform spectrometer (Perkin-Elmer System 2000, KBr). The ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra were recorded on a JNM-ECZ 400R NMR spectrometer at 600 MHz (internal standard TMS). For thin-layer chromatography (TLC), Sorbfil (Russia) and Whatman® UV-254 (Germany) plates were used. As a developer, iodine vapors and a solution of vanillin with sulfuric acid in absolute ethanol were applied.

Plant material

The aerial parts of *Inula britannica* were harvested during the flowering stage in May 2023 in the Bostanlyk district of the Tashkent region.

The species was identified by Dr. Beshko N.Yu. by comparing it with an herbarium specimen from the Herbarium Fund of the Institute of Botany of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Isolation of compounds from *Inula britannica*

Flowers of *Inula britannica* (2 kg) were extracted five times with 93% ethanol at 60 °C for 12 hours per cycle. The combined extracts were concentrated under reduced pressure to a final volume of 1 L. A 100 mL portion of this extract was further evaporated using a rotary evaporator, yielding 38 g of dry extract. This was dissolved in a small volume of ethanol, combined with silica gel in a 1:1 weight ratio, and loaded onto a silica gel column (50 g) for fractionation using sequential elution with extraction petrol, chloroform, ethyl acetate, and methanol.

The chloroform fraction (2.65 g) was then mixed with KSK silica gel (3 g), applied to a silica gel column at a 1:10 (w/w) extract-to-silica gel ratio, and eluted with petroleum ether, followed by mixtures of petroleum ether and ethyl acetate in a polarity gradient, and finally ethanol.

Similarly, the chloroform fraction of the ethanolic extract of the leaves of this plant (120 g from 4.5 kg of leaves) was obtained, part of which was placed on a chromatographic column with silica gel. Elution was performed with a mixture of extraction petrol and its mixtures with EtOAc in a polarity gradient.

Due to the complex mixture of secondary metabolites in the chloroform fraction of the ethanolic extract of the flowers of *Inula britannica* [7], work was conducted to separate the minor components using the

HPLC method. Flexuosin A was isolated from the eluates 58-63 by preparative HPLC.

HPLC

The analysis of eluates 58-63 from the chloroform fraction of the ethanolic extract of *Inula britannica* flowers, containing the sesquiterpene lactone inulonolide, as well as the preparative isolation of components, was carried out using HPLC on an Agilent 1100 chromatograph (Agilent Technologies Inc., USA), equipped with a 4-gradient pump G1311A, degasser G1322A, gradient mixer, variable wavelength detector (VWD) G1314A, and manual loop injector Rheodyne 7725i (Rheodyne, USA) under the following conditions: column Supelco Ascentis C18 (4.6 x 250 mm, Sigma, USA); elution – isocratic, mobile phase composition: acetonitrile/water = 3/7 (v/v); detection – UV 220 nm; flow rate 1 mL/min; retention time of flexuosin A – 8.5 min, inulonolide – 9.4 min.

Flexuosin A (6 α -acetoxy-2 α ,4 β -dihydroxy-1,7 α ,8,10 β (H),15 β (CH₃)-pseudoguaia-11(13)-en-8,12-olid; (3aR,4R,4aS,5R,7R,7aS,8R,9aS)-5,7-dihydroxy-4a,8-dimethyl-3-methylidene-2-oxo-dodecahydroazuleno[6,5-b]furan-4-yl acetate) (**1**) – small colorless crystals isolated from eluates 58-63, with a melting point of 221 °C.

IR spectrum (ν_{max} , KBr, cm^{-1}): 3512, 3479, 3434, 2973, 2937, 1754 (C=O γ -lactone), 1727 (C=O ester), 1639, 1619, 1460, 1410, 1378, 1253, 1168, 1113, 1080, 1030, 978, 945, 865, 818, 709, 541, 475, 438, 422.

^1H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl_3 , δ , ppm, J/Hz): 0.94 (3H, s, H-15), 0.96 (3H, d, J = 6.65, H-14), 1.40 (1H, m, H-9a), 1.85 (2H, m, H-2a, H-7), 1.96 (1H, m, H-1), 2.03 (3H, s, OCOCH₃), 2.05 (1H, m, H-2b), 2.33 (1H, dd, J = 5.7, 14.5, H-9b), 2.37 (1H, ddd, J = 3.3, 4.0, 13.0, H-10), 4.04 (1H, dd, J = 2.3, 10.7, H-6), 4.23 (1H, ddt, J = 3.2, 5.7, 9.3, H-8), 4.94 (1H, ddt, J = 2.1, 4.0, 7.6, H-4), 5.45 (1H, d, J = 3.2, H-13a), 6.18 (1H, d, J = 3.2, H-13b).

^{13}C NMR (150 MHz, CDCl_3 , δ , ppm): 21.35 (C-1), 74.97 (C-2), 38.5 (C-3), 77.33 (C-4), 45.58 (C-5), 80.71 (C-6), 52.86 (C-7), 81.53 (C-8), 38.09 (C-9), 44.1 (C-10), 140.47 (C-11), 170.62 (C-12), 119.89 (C-13), 20.0 (C-14), 19.03 (C-15), 170.00 (OCOCH₃), 29.16 (OCOCH₃).

During column separation of the subfractions, the sesquiterpene lactone ivalin was further isolated.

Ivalin ((3aR,4aS,7S,8aR,9aR)-7-hydroxy-8a-methyl-3,5-dimethylidene-3a,4,4a,6,7,8,9,9a-octahydrobenzo[f][1]benzofuran-2-one) (**2**). The sesquiterpene lactone britanin (**3**) was isolated from the chloroform fraction of the ethanolic extract of flowers (eluate 17 during re-chromatography of eluates 68-98) and leaves (eluate 142) as transparent colorless crystals with a melting point of 128-130 °C.

IR (ν_{max} , KBr, cm^{-1}): 3440, 3392, 3087, 2986, 2963, 2931, 2910, 2834, 1903, 1766, 1726, 1666, 1648, 1538, 1443, 1423, 1385, 1374, 1350, 1296, 1270, 1257, 1215, 1199, 1171, 1159, 1136, 1109, 1089, 1045, 1030, 998, 963, 950, 925, 908, 893, 828, 821, 763, 681, 652, 629, 583, 558, 488, 439, 419, 408.

^1H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl_3 , δ , ppm, J/Hz): 0.84 (3H, s, H-14), 1.2 (1H, t, J = 11.78, H-3a), 1.37 (1H, ddd, J = 1.72, 12.17, 24.42, H-6a), 1.54 (1H, dd, J =

4.78, 15.62, H-1a), 1.72 (1H, br.s., H-5), 1.81 (1H, ddd, $J = 2.39, 6.68, 13.88$, H-6b), 1.84 (1H, dd, $J = 2.2, 12.51$, H-11), 1.91 (1H, ddd, $J = 2.22, 4.47, 12.54$, H-3b), 2.01 (1H, t, $J = 11.67$, H-9a), 2.26 (1H, dd, $J = 1.74, 15.57$, H-1b), 2.68 (1H, ddd, $J = 2.21, 5, 12.23$, H-9b), 3.00 (1H, quintet, $J = 1.7, 5.26, 12.06$, H-7), 3.84 (1H, septet, $J = 4.72, 11.15, 15.92$, H-2), 4.52 (1H, td, $J = 1.69, 4.98$, H-8), 4.56 (1H, q, $J = 1.55, 3.13$, H-15a), 4.89 (1H, q, $J = 1.56, 3.14$, H-15b), 5.61 (1H, d, $J = 1.07, 11.3a$), 6.15 (1H, d, $J = 1.18, 11.3b$).

^{13}C NMR (150 MHz, CDCl_3 , δ , ppm): 41.13 (C-1), 67.12 (C-2), 51.01 (C-3), 141.99 (C-4), 27.33 (C-5), 34.06 (C-6), 40.57 (C-7), 76.70 (C-8), 46.39 (C-9), 45.61 (C-10), 146.05 (C-11), 170.62 (C-12), 120.58 (C-13), 18.82 (C-14), 109.36 (C-15).

During re-chromatography of eluates 68-98 (eluates 13-15) from the chloroform fraction of the ethanolic extract of the flowers and eluates 124-125 from

the chloroform fraction of the ethanolic extract of the leaves, the sesquiterpene lactone britanin (**3**) was isolated. The compound was identified based on spectral data and direct comparison with a standard sample.

X-ray

Transparent crystals of ivalin for X-ray crystallography (RCA) were obtained as thin prismatic crystals. The unit cell parameters of the crystals were determined and refined using a CCD Xcalibur Ruby diffractometer (Oxford Diffraction) equipped with $\text{CuK}\alpha$ radiation at a temperature of 288 K [8]. A complete three-dimensional dataset of reflections was collected using this instrument. Absorption corrections were applied with the SADABS program [9]. The key parameters of the X-ray diffraction experiments and structure refinement are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1

Crystallographic Parameters and X-ray Structural Experiment Characteristics of Ivalin

Parameters	2
Molecular formula	$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_3$
M_r	248.31
Space group, Z	$P2_12_12_1, 8$
$a, \text{Å}$	6.89083(14)
$b, \text{Å}$	11.3869(3)
$c, \text{Å}$	34.7503(7)
$V, \text{Å}^3$	2726.70 (11)
$\rho, \text{g/cm}^3$	1.210
Crystal size (mm)	$0.35 \times 0.25 \times 0.03$
Scanning range θ	2.54-71.48
Number of independent reflections	4775
Number of reflections with $I > 2\sigma(I)$	3873
R_1 ($I > 2\sigma(I)$) and overall	0.045(0.057)
WR_2	0.117
Flack parameter	-0.1(2)
GOOF	1.03
Residual peaks in electron density map ($e \text{ Å}^{-3}$)	0.12 и -0.13
CCDC	2478398

The crystal structures were solved by direct methods using the SHELXS-97 software package [10], and structure refinement was carried out with SHELXL-2014/7 [11]. All non-hydrogen atoms were refined by the full-matrix least squares method based on F^2 in an anisotropic approximation. Hydrogen atoms bonded to carbon were placed in calculated positions and refined using the riding model, with fixed isotropic displacement parameters set at $U_{iso} = nU_{eq}$, where $n = 1.5$ for methyl groups and 1.2 for all other hydrogen atoms (U_{eq} being the equivalent isotropic displacement parameter of the corresponding carbon atoms).

The crystallographic data in CIF format have been deposited at the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre (CCDC).

Cytotoxic activity assays

The transferable cell lines HeLa and HEp-2 were obtained from the Institute of Cytology, Russian Academy of Sciences, Russian Federation. The hepatocyte culture was obtained by our method (Zeomashko et al. 2015). These cell lines are highly sensitive to the effects

of known anticancer drugs. For the cytotoxic test, concentrations of 1, 10, and 100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of nutrient medium were used. As a positive control, the drug cisplatin, containing cis-diaminechloroplatinum, was used as a negative control - cells with culture medium. Cytotoxic activity was investigated by three methods: MTT testing, counting living cells with trypan blue, and morphological analysis. For this procedure, cells were seeded into 96-well plates at a density of 20,000 cells/mL for transplantable cell lines and 50,000 cells/mL for hepatocytes, and incubated at 37 °C in a 5% CO_2 atmosphere. Test substances were added and the cells were further incubated for 24 hours. After this, 20 μL of MTT solution (thiazolyl blue tetrazolium bromide, 5 mg/mL; Sigma, USA) was added to each well, followed by a 4-hour incubation period.

After that the culture medium poured onto 50 μl of dimethylsulfoxide ("Sigma", USA) which was then poured into the cells. After 15 minutes, the EnSpire 2600 spectrophotometer (PerkinElmer, USA), readings were taken at a wavelength of 620 nm. For cell counting using trypan blue, cells were gently detached with

Versene solution. A 50 μL aliquot of the resulting cell suspension was mixed with an equal volume of trypan blue, and the mixture was loaded into a Goryaev chamber for counting. Morphological analysis was carried out using a Leica DMIL microscope (USA) at 80 \times magnification. Statistical analysis and graph plotting were performed using Microsoft Excel, with mean values and standard errors calculated. Differences were considered significant when $p < 0.05$.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 1: Chromatogram of eluates 58-63 from *Inula britannica* during the preparative isolation of components

Based on spectral data, the structure of compound **1** is proposed as 6 α -acetoxy-2 α ,4 β -dihydroxy-1,7 α ,8,10 β (H),15 β (CH₃)-pseudoguai-11(13)-ene-8,12-olide (Figure 2). The trivial name of this pseudoguaianolide is flexuosin A (Figure 2), previously isolated from *Helenium* species [12]. Flexuosin A has been isolated from *Inula britannica* for the first time.

Ivalin

Figure 2: Sesquiterpene lactones from *Inula britannica* and spatial structure of ivalin

A substance **2** was isolated from the chloroform fraction of the ethanol extract of the leaves and flowers in the form of transparent colorless crystals with a melting point of 128-130 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. Based on the analysis of spectral data, compound **2** has the structure 2 α -hydroxy-5,7,8 α (H)-eudesma-4(15),11(13)-dien-8,12-olide (the trivial name is ivalin) (Figure 2). Ivalin has previously been isolated from *Inula britannica* [13]. However, the spatial structure of ivalin has not been previously studied.

Continuing the phytochemical studies of *Inula britannica* flowers [7], minor components of the chloroform fraction of the alcohol extract were investigated by HPLC. The analysis of eluates 58-63 from the chloroform fraction of the ethanol extract of the flowers, containing the guaianolide-type sesquiterpene lactone inulonolide [7], showed that these eluates contained an additional component (Figure 1), which was isolated preparatively.

The spatial structure of ivalin (**2**) was determined by X-ray crystallography. Crystals of **2** are formed by two asymmetric (but stereochemically identical) molecules in the independent part of the unit cell. The experimentally determined Flack parameter of -0.1(2) allows for the independent determination of the absolute configuration of the molecule (as shown in Figure 2), where one of the two molecules is depicted. In both molecules, ring A adopts a chair conformation, the trans-fused ring B adopts a slightly distorted chair conformation, and the cis-lactone ring C adopts a distorted

envelope conformation. The bond lengths and angles are, within the experimental error of 3σ , indistinguishable and are consistent with accepted values [14].

In the crystal of **2** (Figure 2), intermolecular hydrogen bonds of the type O-H...O are observed.

Identical molecules involving the hydroxyl group at C2 and the ketone of the lactone group form chains along the a-axis. The parameters of this O1-H...O3 hydrogen bond are as follows: O1-H, H...O3, O1...O3: 0.91, 1.95, 2.849(5) Å, with an angle of 173(3)°. Other asymmetric molecules join this "pseudo" chain through a hydrogen bond formed between the hydroxyl group (O1'-H') and the acceptor oxygen atom (O1): C2'-O1'-H'...O1.

The geometric parameters of this bond are 0.76, 2.11, 2.853(5), 165(3).

Thus, the spatial structure of eudesmanolide ivalin (**2**), first isolated from the above-ground part of *Inula britannica* L. from the flora of Uzbekistan, has been established.

In addition, a sesquiterpene lactone, britanin (**3**), was isolated from the chloroform fraction of the ethanol extract of the flowers and leaves.

Britanin (**3**) serves as a chemotaxonomic marker of *Inula britannica* and exhibits a broad spectrum of biological activities. It has demonstrated anti-inflammatory and anti-allergic properties [15], and shows potential as a chemotherapeutic agent against gastric cancer (BGC-823) [16]. Additionally, britanin inhibits the proliferation of various cancer cell lines, including breast cancer (MCF-7, MDA-MB-468) [17], rhabdomyosarcoma (RD), breast adenocarcinoma (MCF7), and melanoma (MS) [18]. It also acts as a topoisomerase II inhibitor and suppresses the growth of A549, HepG-2, and HT-29 cancer cells [19], indicating its potential in the treatment of pancreatic cancer as well [20].

We studied the cytotoxic activity of britanin in vitro against cervical cancer cells (HeLa) and laryngeal adenocarcinoma cells (HEp-2). At a concentration of 1 µg/mL, britanin exhibited cytotoxic activity against HeLa and HEp-2 cell lines at the levels of $19.4 \pm 0.5\%$ and $2.8 \pm 0.8\%$, respectively. Increasing the concentration to 10 µg/mL resulted in enhanced inhibition of cell viability, reaching $77.5 \pm 3.3\%$ for HeLa and $79.8 \pm 4.0\%$ for HEp-2. Cisplatin was used as a reference drug and, at a concentration of 1 µg/mL, inhibited the viability of HeLa and HEp-2 cells by $81.6 \pm 3.9\%$ and $52.8 \pm 3.6\%$, respectively. At a higher concentration (10 µg/mL), cisplatin inhibited cell growth by $95.0 \pm 5.0\%$ in HeLa and $89.2 \pm 2.2\%$ in HEp-2 cells. Thus, britanin demonstrates high cytotoxic activity against cervical cancer cells (HeLa) and laryngeal adenocarcinoma cells (HEp-2).

CONCLUSIONS

Continuation of the phytochemical study of the above-ground part revealed the presence of pseudoguaianolides britanin and flexuosin A, as well as eudesmanolide ivalin, for which the spatial structure was determined by X-ray crystallography.

Flexuosin A was isolated from *Inula britannica* for the first time.

The isolated pseudoguaianolide britanin exhibits high cytotoxic activity against cervical cancer cells

(HeLa) and laryngeal adenocarcinoma cells (HEp-2) *in vitro*.

It should be noted that in the study [21], it was suggested that Asian species of *Inula britannica* are characterized by the presence of seco-guaianolides and seco-eudesmanolides. Based on our studies, the Uzbek population may have a new chemotype, as it contains guaianolide (inulonolide), pseudoguaianolides (britanin, inuchinenolide C, flexuosin A), and eudesmanolide (ivalin).

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